

Mitigating Harms in On-Demand Delivery Platforms

AI Regulations, Data Protection, and Workers' Tools

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● ● ● Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly used to manage workers in new forms of work that diverge from the standard employment relationship. While AI-driven technologies, such as algorithmic management and automated decision-making, have the potential to increase efficiency, solve logistics problems, and increase productivity, the increase in managerial power that results from their use has come with a range of social costs, including the expansion of precarious employment and the decrease in the quality of working conditions.¹ Algorithmic and AI-driven management technologies may also generate particular harms to workers of specific status, such as the self-employed, or in specific industries, such as transport and delivery. Therefore, governments, trade unions, local regulators, and industry are increasingly challenged with harnessing the potentials of technological innovation while ensuring that workers and workers' rights are broadly protected.² However, to ensure that an AI-driven world is equitable and sustainable, workers and their representatives must be involved in shaping regulations.

This report uses on-demand delivery work (done by self-employed individuals who deliver food and parcels through algorithmically managed platforms, also referred to as “platform workers” or “gig workers”) as a case study to explore this regulatory challenge and to illustrate the complex relationship between emerging AI technologies and innovations, human workers, and risk.³ We explore the policy gap between UK employment law, data protection regulation, and emerging proposals to regulate AI and related technologies. Furthermore, we examine how trade unions and local workers' collectives have been responding to these risks. We review research literature to provide a deeper illustration of two key risks that emerge from AI-driven

¹ *Algorithmic management: Consequences for work organisation and working conditions.* https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/publications/algorithmic-management-consequences-work-organisation-and-working-conditions_en, accessed 22.05.2024.

² As Nogarede (2021, p. 10) points out, 'of course, whether or not increased productivity translates into better working conditions depends on labour laws and the bargaining power of labour'. <https://feps-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/No-digitalisation-without-representation.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

³ *Protecting workers in the UK platform economy.* <https://fair.work/wp-content/uploads/sites/17/2021/12/Fairwork-UK-Policy-Brief.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

platform work: wage discrimination and racial discrimination. We examine UK- and EU-related proposals to regulate AI in platform work and conclude that while employment law enables some agents to intervene in response to many harms, it will not be sufficient to buffer AI-related risks. Strong data protections are essential to bridge the existing policy gap.

Moreover, workers must play a stronger role in informing regulatory debates. In the absence of government support, trade unions, collaborative research projects involving workers, and workers' collectives have been at the forefront of mitigating risk in the on-demand economy. Workers are making use of data protection laws and developing tools to investigate proprietary data-driven systems and are co-producing evidence of algorithmic harms. In some cases, workers are leading the technical and legal exploration of exploitation in the platform economy.⁴ To date, however, these initiatives have not been incorporated into ongoing regulatory debates.

This report, therefore, asks and answers the following questions:

- How will employment reclassification mitigate risks in on-demand delivery?
- How can current proposed AI regulatory frameworks intervene to address these risks?
- How can workers and their own data-driven interventions in platform risk help shape regulatory debates at transnational, national, or local level?

Answers to these questions will inform broader considerations relating to the AI regulation gap in other spheres and sectors of work. This gap will need to be addressed in the coming years.

⁴ Managed by bots. <https://www.workerinfoexchange.org/wie-report-managed-by-bots>, accessed 22.05.2024.

● ● ● Regulation of AI-Driven Platform Work

On-demand platform workers face myriad risks as well as a double regulatory gap: their employment is not regulated in the UK, nor are the technologies used to control their work.

Many platform workers, to date, have been classified as self-employed contractors and much of the discussion regarding mitigating work-related harms in platform work has centred on the reclassification of gig workers' employment status.⁵ In the UK, court cases have determined that some Uber drivers are "limb (b) workers" while determining that Deliveroo riders remain self-employed.⁶ In the European Union, Spain has passed the "Riders' Law",⁷ while the EU more broadly stands poised to reclassify platform workers through a pan-platform "EU Platform Work Directive".⁸ A draft of this Directive, approved by the European Parliament, proposes the introduction of a "general presumption of employment" and indicates that workers must be informed of and able to bargain on elements of algorithms that affect their work.⁹ The UK currently lacks a clear foundation for addressing the broad issues of misclassification or of bargaining in platform work. The Trades Union Congress (TUC), which represents most trade unions in the UK, regards the misclassification of gig workers as an ongoing issue and supports their reclassification so they can benefit

⁵ Prassl, J., (2017, July), *Who is a worker?* *Law Quarterly Review*, 133(3), 366–372.

⁶ *Aslam v. Uber BV* [2016] UKET 2202551/2015, [51-53] (U.K. Emp. Tribunal), *aff'd*, *Uber BV v. Aslam* [2017] UKEAT 0056/17 (U.K. Emp. Tribunal); *Independent Workers' Union of Great Britain (IWGB) and RooFoods Limited TA/Deliveroo* (2017) Central Arbitration Committee TUR1/985(2016).

⁷ The Riders' Law introduces a "presumption of employment" for "any consumer product or merchandise" which is delivered "through a digital platform" in Spain. The Law was passed in May 2021, but platforms were given three months to prepare for its formal enforcement. <https://braveneweuropa.com/gig-economy-project-spains-riders-law-comes-into-force-heres-what-you-need-to-know>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁸ Report on the proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on improving working conditions in platform work. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2022-0301_EN.html#_section2, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁹ "Workers dealing with algorithmic management and their representatives have to be informed in advance of all elements affecting working conditions and health and security at work, so as to give them the opportunity to understand the functioning of the algorithm and to collectively bargain on it," wrote the European Parliament's Committee on Employment and Social Affairs (EMPL) in its [explanatory statement](#) at the time.

from workers' rights, including the rights to union recognition and the bargaining opportunities that this provides.¹⁰

While reclassification has the potential to mitigate several risks associated with on-demand delivery work, both employees and those assigned worker status would still be subject to AI-driven risks. For example, the use of algorithmic management to “speed up” on-demand deliveries, a core tenet of the rapid commerce economy, will still subject drivers to physical and psychological harm. The use of facial recognition technology to manage workers may still result in discriminatory practices, such as termination without appeal.¹¹ Overall, the reclassification of workers will not prevent the use of AI to control and manage workers, which could continue to result in stress and harm to worker wellbeing.¹² A consideration of the effects of AI is missing from current UK health and safety advice for gig workers.¹³

However, the UK Government's current strategy of empowering existing regulators to develop “context-specific approaches that suit the way AI is actually being used in their sectors”, rather than coordinating an approach to regulating AI,¹⁴ has its limitations. It is clear that while employment status is a necessary, albeit insufficient, condition for ensuring that AI regulations developed in the UK apply to platform workers, it is also important to ensure that on-demand delivery work is “fair work”¹⁵ or “good work”.¹⁶

Four key issues stand out in our report:

¹⁰ *The gig is up: Trade unions tackling insecure work*, p.30. <https://www.tuc.org.uk/research-analysis/reports/gig>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹¹ *Couriers say Uber's “racist facial identification tech got them fired*. <https://www.wired.co.uk/article/uber-eats-couriers-facial-recognition>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹² *The gig economy and psychosocial risk, an interview with Pierre Bérastégui*. <https://www.etui.org/news/gig-economy-and-psychosocial-risk-interview-pierre-berastegui>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹³ *Health and safety for gig economy, agency and temporary workers*. <https://www.hse.gov.uk/vulnerable-workers/gig-agency-temporary-workers/employer/index.htm>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁴ *UK unveils world leading approach to innovation in first artificial intelligence white paper to turbocharge growth*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/uk-unveils-world-leading-approach-to-innovation-in-first-artificial-intelligence-white-paper-to-turbocharge-growth>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁵ “Where fair work drives success, wellbeing and prosperity for individuals, businesses, organisations and for society.” p.5 <https://www.fairworkconvention.scot/the-fair-work-framework/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁶ “Good work – which is not synonymous with traditional employment – is another way in which we can maintain a decent life even in the face of radical changes.” p. 35 https://www.thersa.org/globalassets/pdfs/reports/rsa_good-gigs-fairer-gig-economy-report.pdf, accessed 22.05.2024.

- On-demand workers face ongoing and daily risks. Reducing or removing these risks would require immediate intervention at both national and local levels. In the absence of such interventions, however, workers turn to one another and develop their own inquiries and tools to explore proprietary algorithms and AI-driven risk. Many of these projects rely on strong data protection legislation and use the rights enshrined in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to access and analyse platform data. Current proposed changes to data protection rights in the UK threaten to weaken worker projects and their capacity to inform ongoing regulatory debates.¹⁷
- Strong employment rights will mitigate many risks in on-demand work, but these rights will not necessarily address deeper issues in the use of algorithms, AI, and machine learning to manage and control workers. Employment rights alone will not ensure that platform work is fair or good work. Taking these deeper issues into account would require a coordinated approach to AI regulation, data protection, and employment rights. The EU Platform Work Directive and the EU AI Act offer potential models and trade unions in the UK have already begun to draft recommendations and key principles for platform labour, worker data rights, and the regulation of AI technologies.¹⁸ In devising these, platform workers should be consulted, and local regulators should play a stronger role.
- While the use of AI to control work has, until recently, been a marginal phenomenon in Europe and the UK, the use of AI systems to manage work is not limited to the platform economy.¹⁹ For example, AI is increasingly used for hiring, absence management, performance ratings, and work allocation and has

¹⁷ *Analysis: The UK Data Protection and Digital Information Bill.* <https://www.openrightsgroup.org/publications/analysis-the-uk-data-protection-and-digital-information-bill/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁸ *Work and the AI revolution.* <https://www.tuc.org.uk/Almanifesto>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁹ *No digitalisation without representation: An analysis of policies to empower labour in the digital workplace.* <https://feps-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/No-digitalisation-without-representation.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

been linked with disciplinary processes and worker dismissal.²⁰ These systems will increasingly shape the contemporary experience and power dynamics of the workplace.

- Finally, while power always rests with agents who introduce technological innovations, workers and their representatives are developing vital strategies for making new forms of work fair and good.²¹ Considerable technological innovation is taking place among workers themselves, particularly where the onus is on workers either to prove AI-related harms or to generate evidence. In this way, workers are laying the groundwork for sector-level regulators. Participatory, shared, and co-generated regulation is possible.

● ● ● Executive Summary

The regulation of employment and artificial intelligence (AI) in the platform economy matters at both an individual and social level. The Royal Society for the encouragement of Arts, Manufactures and Commerce (RSA) estimates that there are 1.1 million people in Britain's gig economy.²² These workers increasingly operate in the growing e-commerce environment and with "rapid" (or "quick") commerce infrastructure.²³ The Covid-19 pandemic exacerbated both participation in the gig economy and the growth of rapid commerce.²⁴ The way we work and consume are changing, and innovations in AI, machine learning, and algorithmic management are central to both economies. However, on-demand delivery work can be dangerous work. On-demand platforms are marked by "exploitative practices, which have become widespread and

²⁰ *Technology managing people: The worker experience.* <https://www.tuc.org.uk/research-analysis/reports/technology-managing-people-worker-experience>, accessed 22.05.2024.

²¹ *Seven ways platform workers are fighting back.* <https://www.tuc.org.uk/research-analysis/reports/seven-ways-platform-workers-are-fighting-back>, accessed 22.05.2024.

²² *Good gigs: A fairer future for the UK's gig economy.* https://www.thersa.org/globalassets/pdfs/reports/rsa_good-gigs-fairer-gig-economy-report.pdf, accessed 22.05.2024.

²³ *The platformisation of work in Europe. Highlights from research in 13 European countries.* <https://fepe-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/The-platformisation-of-work-in-Europe.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

²⁴ *Digital technology in freight.* <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/POST-PN-0692/POST-PN-0692.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

institutionalised”.²⁵ Intervening in these work-related risks and exploitative practices requires a concerted effort to bridge the gap between employment rights and the proposed regulation of AI in the UK, as well as strong data protection rights.

Platform Markets: From Margins to Mainstream

The proliferation of platforms in new UK markets over the last decade has resulted in the widespread implementation of AI-driven management technologies that were pioneered in particular sectors, such as on-demand food distribution, introducing new kinds of risks into many different workplaces.²⁶ The expansion of such technologies has rapidly outpaced regulatory initiatives of the government, resulting in risky work environments and leaving workers without rights. Addressing these risks requires bringing together different spheres of regulation, to meet the challenge of developing responses that regulate both the technologies and the industrial relations between workers and platforms.

Rights-Based and Risk-Based: A Dual Approach

Workers’ opportunities to shape or respond to forms of control are often described in terms of rights, while the possible problems associated with AI-driven systems are often denoted in terms of risks. Certain workers’ rights would enable workers to address risks; while certain assessments of technologies on the basis of risk could grant workers certain rights. However, the potential for workers to use rights-based or risk-based systems to address algorithmic and AI-related problems requires significantly more exploration.²⁷ Whichever framework is used, there is a strong case

²⁵ *Protecting workers in the UK platform economy*, p.1. <https://fair.work/wp-content/uploads/sites/17/2021/12/Fairwork-UK-Policy-Brief.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

²⁶ *The rise of the “just-in-time workforce”: On-demand work, crowdwork and labour protection in the gig-economy*. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_protect/---protrav/---travail/documents/publication/wcms_443267.pdf, accessed 22.05.2024.

²⁷ *The AI regulation: Entering an AI regulatory winter?* <https://www.etui.org/publications/ai-regulation-entering-ai-regulatory-winter>, accessed 22.05.2024.

for providing workers with the means to understand the operation of platforms, and to challenge or counteract the risks associated with them. An accurate compendium of risks and harms must be based on workers' experiences. Governments must furnish workers with rights and facilitate both the identification and the eradication of risks and harms created by AI-driven algorithmic management and algorithmic decision-making (ADM).

From Local Responses to Legislative Reform

While certain regulatory frameworks do exist that touch on workers' conditions in the platform economy, these often do not speak to the experiences and demands that workers have on the ground. The litmus test of potential regulation is its practicability for workers in the sector that is being regulated. In the case of on-demand food distribution, an inherently localised sector, putting regulation into practice means addressing local contexts. Methodologically, this report takes on-demand delivery as a case study to examine the way that regulation could help to address risks associated with work. After reviewing scholarship on platform risk, the report surveys the different spheres of regulation that could potentially touch on platform workers' local experiences. It reviews the classification of workers (in UK court cases, the EU Platform Directive, and the Spanish Riders' Law), considers data protection legislation (GDPR and UK Data Protection Acts), and reviews proposed AI regulation (including the EU framework and EU AI Act). It also reviews guides and reports on datafication and work by worker organisations and researchers including Fair Work, the TUC, and The Foundation for European Progressive Studies (FEPS). The report considers worker-revision responses "from below" to risks in platform work, and maps existing and proposed regulation across the UK and EU. In particular, it reviews recent responses to two risks in AI management: wage discrimination and racial profiling. The case studies support the overall findings.

Key Recommendation: A Participative Process of Regulatory Redesign

The three regulatory spheres of data rights, workers' rights, and risk-related regulation of technologies provide significant potential to combine in a system that implements principles for the use of AI-related technologies in platform work. However, as our case studies demonstrate, if better work is the target, workers' voices and initiatives are the trigger to change the ecosystem of platform work to avert the risks described. For workers to be enabled and empowered to use regulation requires not only that regulation is enforced, but that workers have collective voices, for which trade unions must be instrumental, in order to challenge conditions or situations that fail by the standards of regulation. To this end, regulation must be developed in tandem with means for workers to bring cases to the attention of regulators. The development of AI regulation, therefore, should involve a process whereby workers engage in the participatory design of means for monitoring and reporting problems that arise.²⁸

Moreover, there is potential for the regulatory process to enable workers to influence the platforms themselves. Through participatory initiatives involving workers in the drafting and development of regulation, the benefits of technological development can be passed on to workers in a form which they have an active role in determining. The possibilities are huge: for a four-day working week, through space created by productivity gains realised through the automation of mindless work; for new forms of positive social impact; for greater creative freedom; for higher wages; and for many other potential benefits. It is not enough to avoid harmful uses of AI systems – all parties have a positive responsibility to create beneficial outcomes.

Regulatory redesign must have three dimensions. First, there must be strong **data rights**, building on and preserving the principles established in the GDPR.²⁹ Second,

²⁸ See: Lee, M. et al., (2019), *WeBuildAI: Participatory framework for algorithmic governance*, *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 3, CSCW, Article 181 <https://doi.org/10.1145/3359283>; Todolí-Signes, A., (2021), *Making algorithms safe for workers: Occupational risks associated with work managed by artificial intelligence*. *Transfer: European Review of Labour and Research*, 27(4), 433–452. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10242589211035040>, accessed 22.05.2024.

²⁹ *The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is crucial for labour to gain more of a say in the digitisation of the workplace, as personal data is fundamental for many algorithmic systems that are used to monitor and direct the workforce or organise production. GDPR applies regardless of employment status.* <https://feps-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/No-digitalisation-without-representation.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

there must be a review and change of **employment status** for workers working under platforms. Third, there must be a framework of risk to establish the degree of **regulation of the technologies** that certain platforms require in order that the risks they generate can be mitigated.

● ● ● Full Report

Our full report proceeds as follows:

- I. Introduction and literature review: Risk in on-demand delivery
- II. Overview of how regulation and representation can mitigate risks
- III. Deeper exploration of risk
- IV. Wage discrimination
- V. Racial discrimination
- VI. A review of UK and EU approaches to regulating AI in relation to platform work
- VII. Principles and recommendations to ensure workers' influence in regulatory debates

I. Introduction and Literature Review: Risk in On-Demand Delivery

On-demand delivery platforms have expanded in the UK, particularly in the wake of the Covid-19 pandemic.³⁰ These platforms provide the delivery of parcels and goods, groceries, and restaurant meals within short time-frames, such as one-day delivery or

³⁰ *E-commerce in the time of COVID-19*. <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/e-commerce-in-the-time-of-covid-19-3a2b78e8/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

even 15-minute deliveries in the case of “rapid delivery”.³¹ Forecast to grow to £3.3bn in the UK,³² the “quick commerce” economy is made possible by technical innovations in logistics and dispatch, the use of local “dark store” warehouse locations,³³ and the reorganisation of the delivery work process and the flexible scheduling of workers.³⁴

Figure 1. from Delivery Hero,¹ a global on-demand platform for local delivery of food and goods, clearly illustrates this shift.

The on-demand delivery economy relies on speed and efficiency. While technological innovations in AI, machine learning, and algorithmic management aim to meet these goals, quick commerce is also associated with several work-related risks, which have

³¹ Rapid fulfilment of online orders in omnichannel grocery retailing.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2192437622000097>, accessed 22.05.2024.

³² Rapid grocery delivery takes hold across the globe.

<https://www.globalconveniencestorefocus.co.uk/features/rapid-grocery-delivery-takes-hold-across-the-globe>, accessed 22.05.2024.

³³ Back to the Dark Ages? Q-commerce, rapid retail and the changing landscape of retail work. <https://www.uni-europa.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2023/03/Dark-stores-Back-to-the-Dark-Ages.pdf>

³⁴ 11 logistics trends that will drive the industry to embrace smart tech in 2022. https://shippy.io/blogs/logistics-industry-trends-2022/?utm_source=BlogCTA&utm_medium=automation-the-real-magic-behind-quick-commerce

been documented by researchers and workers themselves.³⁵ These risks emerge out of socio-technical interactions or the interplay between social and technical factors.

Evidence abounds of on-demand delivery drivers facing health and safety risks, including the risk of death.³⁶ On-demand delivery work has been linked with heightened concerns for road accidents as workers face exhaustion and fatigue, app-related distractions, as well as pressure to violate traffic regulations in order to meet time pressures.³⁷ Concerns about meeting and maintaining platform rankings are also positively correlated with poor health and mental wellbeing.³⁸ Given these pressures, this work is also associated with general risks to health and wellbeing that spill out from work conditions.³⁹ The Covid-19 pandemic heightened these health risks.⁴⁰

Financial risks and insecurity also affect worker wellbeing.⁴¹ While gig workers fare better than unemployed individuals, financial precarity marks their experience of work.⁴² Many on-demand platform workers are classified as self-employed, meaning

³⁵ Gregory, K., (2021), "My life is more valuable than this': Understanding risk among on-demand food couriers in Edinburgh, *Work, Employment and Society*, 35(2), 316–331. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017020969593> It is important to note that delivery work has, historically, been risky work. The first inquest held under the expansion of the Workmen's Compensation Act of 1906 (UK) was the death of a delivery worker James Hayes, who died while delivering a parcel by bicycle. Hayes "lost control of the machine" and fractured his skull. But delivery work has also been a site of strong worker organisation and worker autonomy, particularly with respect to delivery routes and knowledge of local environments. See: Gallagher, C., (2022), *Cadies, clocks, and the data-driven capital: Incorporating gig workers in Edinburgh*, in Currie, M., Knox, J., & McGregor, C. (Eds.), *Data Justice and the Right to the City*, Edinburgh University Press. Available open access: <https://edinburghuniversitypress.com/book-data-justice-and-the-right-to-the-city.html>, accessed 22.05.2024.

³⁶ Christie, N., & Ward, H., (2019), *The health and safety risks for people who drive for work in the gig economy*. *Journal of Transport & Health*, 115–127. [10.1016/j.jth.2019.02.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2019.02.007), accessed 22.05.2024.

³⁷ Christie, N., Ward, H., & Helman, S., (2017), *The changing nature of driving for work and questions for safety policy, and practice*. <https://www.pacts.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/ORR-SH-HW-and-NC-May-2017.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

³⁸ *Mental well-being platform workers under pressure*. <https://www.eur.nl/en/news/mental-well-being-platform-workers-under-pressure>, accessed 22.05.2024.

³⁹ *Health and safety risks faced by delivery riders during the COVID-19 pandemic*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214140522000159>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁴⁰ Apouey, B. et al., (2020), *Gig workers during the COVID-19 crisis in France: Financial precarity and mental well-being*. *J Urban Health*, 97, 776–795. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11524-020-00480-4>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁴¹ Wood, A., & Lehdonvirta, V., (2021, March 31), *Platform precarity: Surviving algorithmic insecurity in the gig economy*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3795375> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3795375>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁴² *National survey of mental health and life satisfaction of gig workers: The role of loneliness and financial precarity*. <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/12/12/e066389.abstract>, accessed 22.05.2024.

that they are not entitled to sick pay and holiday pay.⁴³ This work is also often flexibly or “hyper-flexibly” scheduled,⁴⁴ leading to unstable and precarious employment and unpredictable or “non-standard” work routines, which results in unstable wages over time.⁴⁵ Furthermore, algorithmic reward systems delink time and pay, resulting in unpredictable amounts of uncompensated working time, while dynamic pricing results in unpredictable and fluctuating incomes and creates poverty and precarity.⁴⁶ Predictive behavioural profiling can result in allocated work not providing workers with a sufficient income to make a living.⁴⁷ Covid-19 exacerbated these issues, and rising living costs are bearing down on workers.⁴⁸

Fair Work, a research project, reports that “predatory and exploitative labour practices have become widespread and institutionalised across the platform economy”.⁴⁹ Research indicates that gig workers in the United States face difficult working conditions, including unstable and low wages and lost earnings due to technical difficulties with proprietary systems.⁵⁰ The Economic Policy Institute (US) also reports that one in five gig workers surveyed have gone hungry because they

⁴³ Given the lack of health and safety measures, workers may also feel pressure to work while sick. Gregory, K., (2021), “My life is more valuable than this’: Understanding risk among on-demand food couriers in Edinburgh, *Work, Employment and Society*, 35(2), 316–331.

⁴⁴ Algorithmic insecurity, schedule nonstandardness, and gig worker wellbeing. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3773164, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁴⁵ Informalization in gig food delivery in the UK: The case of hyper-flexible and precarious work. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/irel.12320>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁴⁶ Workers’ recommendations on the draft EU Platform Work Directive, p.11. <https://www.workerinfoexchange.org/workers-recommendations-on-eu-directive>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁴⁷ Automated dismissal decisions, data protection and the law of unfair dismissal. <https://uklabourlawblog.com/2021/10/19/automated-dismissal-decisions-data-protection-and-the-law-of-unfair-dismissal-by-philippa-collins/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁴⁸ “Our analysis revealed that 3 weeks into the lockdown, 56% of our overall sample had stopped working and respondents had experienced a 28% income drop on average. Gig economy drivers reported a significant 20 percentage point larger income decrease than other workers in our sample” from Apouey, B., et al., (2020), *Gig workers during the COVID-19 crisis in France: Financial precarity and mental well-being*. *J Urban Health*, 97, 776–795. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11524-020-00480-4>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁴⁹ Protecting workers in the UK platform economy. <https://fair.work/wp-content/uploads/sites/17/2021/12/Fairwork-UK-Policy-Brief.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁵⁰ National survey of gig workers paints a picture of poor working conditions, low pay. <https://www.epi.org/publication/gig-worker-survey/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

could not afford enough to eat.⁵¹ These harms are also experienced globally by gig workers. They are the result of platform business models rather than geography.⁵²

The employment status of on-demand delivery workers, fundamental to platform business models, underpins these risks as many platforms rely on self-employed contractors to complete work on a paid-per-task basis. As self-employed contractors, the risks of doing business have been “demutualised” or shifted primarily or entirely to the worker.⁵³ As such, self-employed individuals are responsible for providing their own work-related equipment, as well maintaining their own health and safety.⁵⁴

Gig workers’ employment status has received considerable attention in courts across the world.⁵⁵ It is essential to note that many self-employed gig workers are simultaneously the labour force of the “gig economy” and of the “platform economy”. While these terms overlap, the regulation of gig work through labour law is not the same as the regulation of technology and data rights in the platform economy. While the European Union’s Platform Work Directive attempts to draw these regulatory frameworks closer,⁵⁶ in the UK there is a considerable policy gap between the regulation of gig work and the proposed regulation of data-driven technology. This gap has been referred to as a “taxonomical quandary” that will require concerted

⁵¹ National survey of gig workers paints a picture of poor working conditions, low pay. <https://www.epi.org/publication/gig-worker-survey/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁵² Bajwa, U., Gastaldo, D., Di Ruggiero, E. et al. (2018) *The health of workers in the global gig economy*. *Global Health* 14, 124.

⁵³ DeStefano, V., (2016), *Introduction: Crowdsourcing, the gig-economy and the law*. *Comparative Labor Law & Policy Journal*, 37(3), 461–470. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2767383, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁵⁴ *Risk shifts in the gig economy: The normative case for an insurance scheme against the effects of precarious work*. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/jopp.12233>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁵⁵ *Gig economy workers in the European Union: Towards changing their legal classification*. https://www.cidob.org/en/articulos/revista_cidob_d_afers_internacionals/131/gig_economy_workers_in_the_european_union_towards_changing_their_legal_classification, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁵⁶ *EU rules on platform work*. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/platform-work-eu/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

government efforts to bridge.⁵⁷ As a result, legal scholars note that there is a “long road” to effective health and safety rights for on-demand workers in the UK.⁵⁸

Employment law is well-suited to mitigate some of the risks that on-demand delivery workers face. Legal reform could offer workers employment status, social security, holiday pay, and minimum wage, as well as rights to health and safety standards. Employment rights, by offering stability and safety, may also mitigate mental health and wellbeing concerns among gig workers. However, worker or employment status will not necessarily mitigate risks that follow on from the use of AI and machine learning to manage workers and control labour processes. In the case of on-demand delivery, human workers are needed to adapt data-driven on-demand business models to local environments.⁵⁹ As such, these workers are imbricated in technical systems composed of proprietary data, algorithms, machine learning, automated decision making, and artificial intelligence.⁶⁰ For example, proprietary algorithmic management meant to ensure rapid delivery will continue to incentivise risk by workers and will continue to “black box” crucial information from workers.⁶¹ Facial recognition technology, such as that used to onboard workers in companies such as Deliveroo, may still be complicit in unfair worker terminations.⁶²

⁵⁷ *Between risk mitigation and labour rights enforcement: Assessing the transatlantic race to govern AI-driven decision-making through a comparative lens.* Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4337517>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁵⁸ *Beyond status: The long road towards effective health and safety rights for on-demand workers.* <https://uklabourlawblog.com/2021/06/16/beyond-status-the-long-road-towards-effective-health-and-safety-rights-for-on-demand-workers-by-aude-cefaliello/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁵⁹ *Designing technology for on-demand delivery: The effect of customer tipping on crowdsourced driver behaviour and last mile performance.* <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/joom.1187>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁶⁰ For working definitions of the terms “Algorithm”, “Machine Learning”, “Automated Decision Making”, “Artificial Intelligence”, we recommend the following report: <https://www.tuc.org.uk/sites/default/files/2022-08/People-Powered-Technology-2022-Report-AW.pdf> For further reading, see the “AI for Fair Work” report: <https://fair.work/wp-content/uploads/sites/17/2022/12/AI-for-fair-work-report-edited.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁶¹ *The algorithmic management of work and its implications in different contexts.* <https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-06/JRC129749.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁶² *Courier sues Uber Eats over “racist” facial recognition dismissal.* <https://www.uktech.news/ai/uber-eats-racist-ai-dismissal-20220728>, accessed 22.05.2024.

These datafied systems enable platforms to coordinate and control both the logistics and labour of the delivery process.⁶³ Described as “algorithmic management”,⁶⁴ this arrangement has been associated with six mechanisms through which algorithms assert control over workers: by restricting and recommending; evaluating workers by recording and rating; and disciplining workers by rewarding and replacing. The term “algorithmic insecurity” has been coined as a way to frame how algorithms and AI-driven systems undermine workers’ control over the work process. In fact, as several recent court cases have borne out, platforms’ proprietary technical systems have been implicated in discrimination in shift distribution,⁶⁵ failure to honour workers’ rights to understand the context and substance of automated algorithmic decision making,⁶⁶ and unfair driver fines.⁶⁷

Creating closer links between employment regulation and the regulation of AI is vital if the government intends to intervene meaningfully in the complex socio-technical systems that shape contemporary working conditions for millions of people in the UK and beyond.⁶⁸ Trade unions have begun to do research here, despite the lack of consultation and a coordinated approach between government, industry, and other

⁶³ Meal delivery logistics and the agencies of distribution in urban economies of food provision in the UK. <https://journals.openedition.org/articulo/4562#tocto2n1>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁶⁴ Algorithmic management: Its implications for information systems research. <https://www.alexandria.unisg.ch/server/api/core/bitstreams/1ee6d1cf-a984-4e91-84e4-ea527e885c40/content>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁶⁵ “In a landmark case decided in July 2021, the Court of Bologna, Italy found that Deliveroo delivery drivers had been discriminated against based on an automated reliability index. The reliability index exhibited significant influence on the shifts offered to delivery drivers but did not take extenuating circumstances into account for absences that negatively impacted their reliability score.” <https://oecd.ai/en/wonk/workplace-regulation-2022>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁶⁶ “In June 2021, Foodinho, another platform delivery firm, was found to violate [several GDPR provisions](#) in its algorithmic management of workers. Foodinho failed to provide riders with the right to contest algorithmic decision-making or request human alternatives on decisions that scored them and impacted their employment opportunities. Foodinho also violated [Article 13](#) of the GDPR, failing to disclose the logic and motivation for processing personal data” <https://oecd.ai/en/wonk/workplace-regulation-2022>

⁶⁷ “In March 2021, Ola, a rideshare company, was also found to violate [Article 22 of the GDPR](#) for using an automated AI system to detect invalid rides and, consequently, fine drivers.” <https://oecd.ai/en/wonk/workplace-regulation-2022>

⁶⁸ The proportion of the global workforce engaged in platform work has grown rapidly: https://ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---cabinet/documents/publication/wcms_814417.pdf

stakeholders.⁶⁹ It is also important to note that there are calls for regulation at local city level across the United States,⁷⁰ the UK,⁷¹ and Europe.⁷²

Furthermore, it is widely accepted that fair labour practices depend on workers having a voice and a stake in decisions made, as well as being informed about their conditions of work in order that they can bargain.⁷³ Here, fundamental principles of industrial relations, such as the International Labour Organisation's (ILO) internationally agreed principle of the right to bargain collectively, have to be considered in terms of the changes to work that are resulting from new platform working. AI regulation, for example, must not supplant or substitute workers' efforts to access information or develop the collective capacity to bargain and improve platform work. These challenges require observation of platforms both "upstream" and "downstream": to observe what technological systems are being developed and how they operate; to observe how they impact workers; and to observe how these systems alter workers' knowledge and understanding of their work. In short, a regulatory system must be dynamic enough to enable workers themselves to monitor new technologies and to understand how they will impact on their work and lives.

Across many on-demand platforms, this upstream and downstream observation is already taking place. For example, in the absence of existing labour or technology regulations, workers in the platform economy have initiated their own "non-regulatory" data-driven projects to observe the "black boxed" functioning of platforms, as well as to intervene in situations of work-related risks. Worker Info Exchange, for example, has used worker data gathered through subject-access requests to mount court cases, employment tribunal cases, and legal claims against Uber and other major

⁶⁹ Algorithmic transparency and accountability in the world of work. <https://www.ituc-csi.org/Algorithmic-transparency-and-accountability>

⁷⁰ Rapid growth in food deliveries means regulators must clarify safety responsibilities. <https://www.pewtrusts.org/en/research-and-analysis/articles/2020/06/18/rapid-growth-in-food-deliveries-means-regulators-must-clarify-safety-responsibilities>

⁷¹ Edinburgh task force driving change for the gig economy. <https://www.edinburgh.gov.uk/news/article/13449/edinburgh-task-force-driving-change-for-the-gig-economy>

⁷² "Dark commerce" backlash grows in cities across Europe. <https://www.politico.eu/article/dark-commerce-rules-ramp-up-as-stores-shut-down/>

⁷³ The principle of knowing your pay is in the Employment Relations Act. The principle of Collective Bargaining is established by the ILO.

platforms relating to hidden unfair algorithmic management.⁷⁴ WeClock, a free, open source self-tracking app, allows workers to discover how much of their time is spent on work.⁷⁵ RooParse is a tool that enables delivery workers to parse data from invoices to better monitor their rates of pay.⁷⁶ And PersonalDataIO helps workers to exercise their rights over their personal data, with a bot that, with a few inputs by users, contacts companies and executes users' requests.⁷⁷ These are just a few of the “non-regulatory” data-driven projects that are beginning to emerge globally among platform workers.⁷⁸

These projects have, to date, been disregarded in policy considerations, yet they offer useful and tangible ways of understanding worker needs with respect to data protection and technology more broadly. They also demonstrate the gap between regulations and practical results. In the words of PersonalDataIO: “It is nice to have rights. It is better we can effectively use them.”⁷⁹

II. Overview of Regulation and Representation to Mitigate Risk

Self-employed workers have relatively few resources to mitigate risk in the on-demand economy. However, workers and representatives have mobilised to demand reforms to employment law and data protection law, and have taken up their own projects to intervene in day-to-day work. Truly mitigating risk in on-demand platform work, however, sits at the intersection of several ongoing debates across labour law, AI regulation, data governance, and collective labour rights.⁸⁰

In Table 1, we present five spheres (employment status, regulation of AI, data rights, trade unions, and worker initiatives) that could be drawn on to mitigate risks for on-

⁷⁴ <https://www.workerinfoexchange.org>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁷⁵ <https://weclock.it>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁷⁶ <https://workersobservatory.org/new-tool-to-track-courier-pay-over-time/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁷⁷ <https://personaldata.io>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁷⁸ See “Digital Worker Inquiry” held at the University of Edinburgh (October 2021) <https://digitalworkerinquiry.com/project.html>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁷⁹ <https://www.legalgeek.co/startup-map/personaldata-io/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁸⁰ Collective labour rights include the rights to form unions, collectively bargain, and organise.

<https://www.tuc.org.uk/sites/default/files/2021-11/Platform%20essays%20with%20polling%20data.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

demand food delivery drivers. While employment status is set by determining a categorical relationship, the cutting-edge regulation of AI to date has been driven by risk-assessment frameworks that seek to gauge the potential for a particular system to result in harm, and to require measures to mitigate or prevent these risks from coming to pass. These spheres do not necessarily speak easily to one another, particularly in the absence of pan-platform legislation (such as the EU's Platform Work Directive). Nevertheless, it is worth delineating the state of these spheres in relation to known risks associated with on-demand food delivery work (see Table 1).

Risk in On-Demand Delivery	Employment Status	Regulation of AI	Data Rights	Trade Unions	Worker Initiatives
<p>Health & safety</p>	<p>Currently, self-employed workers “have health and safety responsibilities for both themselves and anyone who is affected by their work.”</p> <p>Limb (b) status would require “businesses to have the same health and safety duties towards such workers as it has towards its other employees.”</p> <p>Gig economy, agency and temporary workers - Definitions - HSE</p> <p>Limb (b) workers are covered by the Employment Rights</p>	<p>Workers are driven by algorithmic systems to “speed” and they are subject to app-determined routes.</p> <p>AI-driven systems privilege speed and efficiency. Speedy delivery is deadly, but workers are punished by rating and ranking if goals are not met.</p> <p>UK Gov establishes five principles to regulate AI, including safety, but these are devolved to the existing health & safety regulator.</p> <p>UK unveils world leading approach to innovation in first</p>	<p>Access to platform data is useful and may be essential to workers and organisers.</p> <p>WP 2020.05 GDPR Working conditions digital labour platforms Silberman Johnston web.pdf (etui.org)</p>	<p>Union health and safety reps have statutory rights to undertake health and safety inspections, which could be used to inspect the impact of AI systems on workers.</p> <p>In addition, there are certain rights under the Information and Consultation of Employee Regulations (ICE) according to which workers must be consulted about possible redundancies and changes to terms and conditions of employment, which ACAS says could apply to changes affecting</p>	<p>Workers currently have little support with respect to safety.</p> <p>Workers use backchannels such as WhatsApp and social media forums to discuss safety and how best to negotiate local working environments.</p>

	<p>Act 1996, as amended, against suffering any harm because of any reasonable actions they take on health and safety grounds.</p> <p>Employment protection (hse.gov.uk)</p> <p>This combination of statutes and regulations creates a safety net applicable to limb (b) workers in terms of occupational safety and health (OSH): the employer is responsible for their health and safety and should evaluate potential risks caused by the way that it conducts its undertaking.</p> <p>Beyond status: the long road towards effective health and</p>	<p>artificial intelligence white paper to turbocharge growth - GOV.UK (www.gov.uk)</p> <p>According to the EU Platform Directive (Amendment 29): “Artificial intelligence usage on platforms should uphold the health, safety, privacy and working conditions of platform workers.”</p> <p>REPORT on the proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on improving working conditions in platform work A9-0301/2022 European Parliament (europa.eu)</p> <p>EU AI Act determines employers’</p>		<p>physical and mental wellbeing.</p> <p>(People Powered Technology 2022 Report, p.18)</p>	
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	<p>safety rights for on-demand workers – by Aude Cefaliello – UK Labour Law (uklabourlawblog.com)</p> <p>This would, for example, mean workers could not be terminated for refusing to follow routes deemed most efficient, if they felt the route was unsafe.</p> <p>Food delivery drivers fired after ‘cut-price’ GPS app sent them on ‘impossible’ routes Couriers/delivery industry The Guardian</p>	<p>responsibilities in preventing AI risks.</p> <p><i>Expert explainer: The EU AI Act proposal Ada Lovelace Institute</i></p>			
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<p>Mental health</p>	<p>Limb (b) status protection would require businesses to have the same health and safety duties towards such workers as it has towards its other employees.</p>	<p>“Pervasive monitoring allowed by AI-supported digital monitoring technologies can have a negative impact in particular on workers’ mental health. [...] The use of data for example to reward, penalise or even exclude workers could lead to feelings of insecurity and stress.”</p> <p>Beyond status: the long road towards effective health and safety rights for on-demand workers - by Aude Cefaliello - UK Labour Law (uklabourlawblog.com)</p>	<p>Access to data may be useful and could be essential to workers who are facing issues of pervasive monitoring.</p> <p>WP 2020.05 GDPR Working conditions digital labour platforms Silberman Johnston web.pdf (etui.org)</p>	<p>Union health and safety rights extend to mental health. In addition, ICE may also apply.</p>	<p>Workers currently have little support with respect to mental health. Workers may be using apps or other tools for support.</p> <p>The gig economy is taking a toll on UK workers' mental health LSE Business Review</p>
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<p>Wage discrimination</p>	<p>Limb (b) status would provide for minimum wage protection, unfair deductions from wages, and right to an itemised pay slip.</p> <p>Deliveroo has also pledged to pay all its riders National Minimum Wage, but only when they are actively delivering. This is not currently enforceable.</p>	<p>Wages are set algorithmically, dynamically.</p> <p>Issues related to working time: - definition of working time - compensation of excessive waiting time.</p> <p>Algorithmic workplace explainability. Even more than transparency, what is needed is explainability. "Slave to the Algorithm? Why a 'Right to an Explanation' Is Probably No" by Lilian Edwards and Michael Veale (duke.edu)</p>	<p>Access to data is essential. WP 2020.05 GDPR Working conditions digital labour platforms Silberman Johnston web.pdf (etui.org)</p>	<p>Unions have resources and capacity to lobby on changing the classification of workers, such as in the case of Uber.</p> <p>Seven ways platform workers are fighting back, p.6-7)</p> <p>This results in extending wage protections to gig workers.</p> <p>Unions are also able to support workers to monitor their pay in order to establish inequality of pay.</p>	<p>Workers are tracking wages through tools, such as Rooparse or the Wage Theft Calculator. Digital Worker Inquiry: Data, Solidarity, Leverage</p>
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<p>Predictable scheduling</p>	<p>Would allow for some protection.</p>	<p>Essential.</p>	<p>Access to data is essential. WP 2020.05 GDPR Working conditions digital labour platforms Silberman Johnston web.pdf (etui.org)</p>	<p>Unions have resources and capacity to support workers to monitor their schedules in order to establish their predictability, but without any bargaining agreements they have little capacity to improve these.</p>	<p>Workers are tracking time through tools such as WeClock. Home page (weclock.it)</p>
<p>Racial bias and discrimination</p>	<p>Would allow for some protection.</p>	<p>Essential.</p>	<p>Access to data is essential. WP 2020.05 GDPR Working conditions digital labour platforms Silberman Johnston web.pdf (etui.org)</p>	<p>Whistleblowing and exposure, such as the letter IWGB sent concerning struck-off riders. Couriers say Uber's 'racist' facial identification tech got them fired WIRED</p>	<p>Workers are fighting in courts. «Les chauffeurs Uber vont enfin pouvoir défendre leurs intérêts» - 20 minutes</p>

<p>Privacy, surveillance</p>	<p>Would allow for some protection.</p>	<p>EU AI ACT: Privacy and data protection rules.</p>	<p>GDPR rights are potentially extensive in platform work, but must be used and enforceable.</p> <p>The monitoring of workers is regulated by national laws that often predate GDPR and do not cover modern and intrusive people analytics. (Eurofound, 2020; Moore, 2020).</p> <p>WP 2020.05 GDPR Working conditions digital labour platforms Silberman Johnston web.pdf (etui.org)</p>	<p>Recognition agreements could lead to agreements with provisions on surveillance.</p>	<p>Workers are exploring the potential and limits of GDPR through projects such as Worker Info Exchange and PersonalDataIO.</p> <p>Worker Info Exchange Data Rights for Digital Workers London</p> <p>Wikibase Personal data</p>
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Unfair termination	Would allow for some protection.	The regulator should prohibit algorithms that can be used to terminate the employment relationship or are the de facto sole decision-maker about workers (Ponce del Castillo, 2021).	Access to data is essential. WP 2020.05 GDPR Working conditions digital labour platforms Silberman Johnston web.pdf (etui.org)	By securing classification of gig workers as limb (b) workers, they would still not enjoy statutory protection from unfair dismissal. However, the right to join a union could lead to agreements on termination.	Workers are fighting unfair termination in courts. Uber and Lyft drivers in California say they've been spontaneously fired by apps, report finds (nbcnews.com)
Platform closure	Employment status may ensure some benefits, such as severance pay.	AI regulation should explore how platforms innovations “travel” between platforms or workplaces so that known harms can be flagged or mitigated.	Access to data may be needed after a platform has closed. For example, workers may require evidence of work history or performance.	Trade unions may offer support to workers who find themselves unexpectedly out of work due to platform closure.	Workers have little recourse if a platform unexpectedly closes. Mobile workers, contingent labour: Migration, the gig economy and the multiplication of labour - Moritz Altenried, 2024 (sagepub.com)

Table 1. Five spheres of engagement to mitigate risk for on-demand food delivery drivers

III. Deeper Exploration of Risk

This section considers in more detail the potential to regulate two of the risks facing on-demand distribution workers: (A) algorithmic wage discrimination and (B) algorithmic racial profiling. It examines both risks by: (1) offering a general definition of the AI-related problem in its application to workplaces; (2) presenting perspectives on the issue from both sides of the unregulated space, (2.1) workers, advocacy groups, trades unions and (2.2) platforms; (3) considering general principles that could inform the regulation of this area; (4) exploring how these principles are currently embedded in UK employment regulation and employment law; (5) discussing ways in which AI risk frameworks and AI regulation might be relevant to these questions; and (6) examining ways that workers, within or in the absence of regulation, are taking autonomous action to address the risks.

A. Algorithmic Wage Discrimination

1. AI-Related Problem in the Workplace

Within the on-demand delivery economy, most food delivery workers cannot accurately predict their incomes, and incur the risks of unpredictable, unstable, and frequently declining income.⁸¹ On platforms such as UberEats and Deliveroo, rates are algorithmically determined, meaning that even an accurate record of working time and distance travelled will not enable workers to explain or calculate their earnings accurately. Identical work patterns might result in different pay at different times, higher or lower pay than that received by workers doing very similar work in the same town, or different average rates to those earned by workers in nearby towns. Such “dynamic pricing” results in wages being set based on a variety of data inputs: market supply, consumer demand, actions of competitors, previous data provided by workers

⁸¹ *Digital labour platforms and the future of work: Towards decent work in the online world.* https://www.ilo.org/global/publications/books/WCMS_645337/lang--en/index.htm, accessed 22.05.2024.

or consumers, etc. These inputs are unknown to the workers.⁸² Algorithmically personalised wage systems, often known as “dynamic pay”, have been found to result in forms of wage discrimination.⁸³

2.1 Perspective of Workers, Worker Advocacy Groups, and Trades Unions on the Issue

Workers’ awareness of the risk of wage discrimination is reflected in local initiatives to monitor and identify uneven and unequal payments. In Dunfermline, UberEats and Just Eat workers noticed that their rates were fluctuating and not aligning with the rates of their peers or workers in nearby Kirkcaldy.⁸⁴ They recorded a sample of orders that enabled them to establish the average rates they were being paid, and thus to monitor rate fluctuations. Trade unions and confederations, as well as a range of other research initiatives, have been looking to develop training and skills that could equip workers to gain more insight and capacity to calculate and explain their wages.⁸⁵

2.2 Perspectives of Platforms on the Issue

Platforms have publicly described the complexity of rate-setting systems and their implementation. For instance, Uber has told riders that whereas they formerly “set prices based on time and distance and then surge helped increase the price when demand was highest”, it now has developed “advanced technology that uses years of

⁸² “Most platforms now commonly use algorithms to drive dynamic pay-rate setting systems. This means that pay is set at variable rates decided in real time by a platform algorithm depending upon consumer and labour market conditions.” Worker advocacy organisation WIX said in February 2023, on its recommendations on the EU platform directive.

⁸³ On algorithmic wage discrimination. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4331080 p. 7

“Workers who are doing the same work, with the same skill, for the same company, at the same time, may receive different hourly pay.”

⁸⁴ Gallagher, C., Gregory, K. & Karabaliev, B. (2023) Digital worker inquiry and the critical potential of participatory worker data science for on-demand platform workers. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 1–21.

⁸⁵ [A Trade Union Guide for Trainers on Crowd-, App-, and Platform-Based Work](#), accessed 22.05.2024.

data and learning to find a competitive price for the time of day, location and distance of the trip”.⁸⁶

3. General Principles That Could Inform Regulation in This Area

Equal pay for equal work. This principle is embedded in different ways in US, EU, and UK employment law.⁸⁷ Workers have different pay-related rights based on their classification. Even where this rule is not seen to apply to food delivery workers, they might appeal to the principle that people should not be paid less because of their race or their gender. A recent article found there to be a gender earnings gap in the gig economy, due to the way that the algorithm rewarded different workers’ experience, their preferences and constraints over where to work, and their preferences for driving speed.⁸⁸

4. How These Principles Are Currently Embedded in UK Regulation and Law

Under the UK **Equality Act** 2010, it is legal to pay employees different wages for the same or a similar job, or for work of equal value, if there are non-discriminatory material factors that explain the reason for the difference. If the reasons for differences paid for equal tasks included factors that discriminated on the basis of race, gender, or any other protected characteristic, then workers are entitled to raise a grievance or make an equal pay claim to an employment tribunal.⁸⁹ However, if food delivery workers are classified as self-employed then these principles do not apply.

⁸⁶ ADCU dismisses Uber's pay increase announcement as a shell game scam. <https://www.adcu.org.uk/news-posts/adcu-dismisses-ubers-pay-increase-announcement-as-a-shell-game-scam>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁸⁷ Equal pay for equal work. <https://www.dol.gov/agencies/oasam/centers-offices/civil-rights-center/internal/policies/equal-pay-for-equal-work>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁸⁸ The gender earnings gap in the gig economy: Evidence from over a million rideshare drivers. <https://academic.oup.com/restud/article-abstract/88/5/2210/6007480>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁸⁹ <https://www.acas.org.uk/equal-pay/advice-for-employees>, accessed 22.05.2024.

It is also possible that dynamic pay is in violation of the provision in the **Employment Rights Act** (ERA) that all workers should be told what their pay is.⁹⁰ However, in the UK, pay transparency applies only to workers and not to self-employed people.⁹¹ In the EU, the European Parliament recently voted in favour of a Platform Worker Directive which sets out a “general presumption of employment” for gig workers. Were something similar applied in the UK, regulations like those defined in the ERA would apply to platform workers.

However, even where gig workers are classified as workers, the opacity of dynamic pricing and wage setting makes it difficult for them or their advocates to see if discriminatory systems are in use in determining their wages.⁹²

The **GDPR** allows workers to obtain some data that might help establish their rates. These rights are unconnected with employment rights or classification. The GDPR contains rules on the collection, storage, and use (processing) of personal data, including that of platform workers.⁹³ It is unclear whether processing of data relating to the employment relationship is regulated in the same way as consumer, citizen, and other kinds of data.⁹⁴ However, it does (a) provide workers with rights to access any data that they have inputted, or that has been observed about them. These data might enable them to establish details about their own pay and compare it with that of others. It stipulates that (b) personal data must be “processed lawfully, fairly and in a

⁹⁰ Section 1 of the Employment Rights Act. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1996/18/section/1>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁹¹ Employment status and employment rights: Guidance for HR professionals, legal professionals and other groups. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/employment-status-and-employment-rights/employment-status-and-employment-rights-guidance-for-hr-professionals-legal-professionals-and-other-groups>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁹² The principle of pay transparency is closely linked to, but different from, the principle of calculative fairness. This principle establishes the importance of the wage-setting process: workers should be paid in ways that are fair. If the operation of dynamic pricing systems is unknown, then the principle of their calculative fairness cannot be established.

⁹³ Constitutional values in the gig-economy? Why labor law fails at platform work, and what can we do about it? <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-4698/11/3/86#B30-societies-11-00086>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁹⁴ “To simplify the underlying rationale of data protection law to the extreme, the protection of privacy—or, in other contexts, the minimum of individual rights, human dignity—constitutes the core that must be taken into account at all times. For employment-related data processing, the standard in many legal systems (including the Hungarian system) is the rule that data processing is justifiable in labor relations as long as it is related to the employment relationship.” <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-4698/11/3/86>, accessed 22.05.2024.

transparent manner”, and that data processing must be compliant with other laws, including the Equality Act. It requires that (c) processing of data is not “unduly detrimental, unexpected, or misleading” to data subjects.⁹⁵ It (d) forbids discriminatory profiling on the basis of race or ethnic origin, among other protected characteristics.⁹⁶ And (e) it stipulates that a data subject has a right “not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her.”⁹⁷ Together, these provisions create a set of measures through which workers may be able to obtain information about their wages.

These provisions raise questions, too: How are workers to know whether data is being processed in ways that breach these regulations, if they are not able to understand what data is being used, and how? And how will the UK Data Protection Act alter aspects of GDPR?⁹⁸

5. How AI Risk Frameworks and AI Regulation Might Be Relevant to These Questions

The UK Government currently lacks an approach to the regulation of AI that considers its impact on platform work, although its broad approach to the regulation of AI indicates an awareness of this policy gap. Meanwhile, discussion of AI regulation in the EU has generated a series of principles within a risk-based framework. This regulatory development points to the potential for AI regulation to help enable gig workers to navigate risks around wage discrimination. Section IV of this report outlines the current UK approach to the regulation of AI.

⁹⁵ This is the UK Information Commissioner’s Office’s parsing of the “fairness” principle of the GDPR. <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-protection-principles/a-guide-to-the-data-protection-principles/the-principles/lawfulness-fairness-and-transparency/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁹⁶ In Recital 71, the GDPR advises that organisations should avoid any form of profiling that results in “discriminatory effects on natural persons on the basis of racial or ethnic origin, political opinion, religion or beliefs, trade union membership, genetic or health status or sexual orientation, or processing that results in measures having such an effect.” <https://www.privacy-regulation.eu/en/recital-71-GDPR.htm>, accessed 22.05.2024.

⁹⁷ The ICO specifies that organisations have proactive obligations to bring details of these rights to the attention of individuals.

⁹⁸ UK takes another bite at post-Brexit data protection reform – with “new GDPR”. <https://techcrunch.com/2023/03/08/uk-data-reform-bill-no-2/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

6. How Workers, Within or in the Absence of Regulation, Are Taking Autonomous Action to Address the Risk

In Dunfermline, workers detected that their rates of pay were lower than in nearby Kirkcaldy, and also established that different riders in the town received different rates.⁹⁹ This came to light through sharing screenshots of orders, allowing them to identify a rough formula as to the rates they were paid, and therefore to see when their own rates fell above and below the average. This was an instance of a dynamic pay system that set wages on undisclosed data inputs, making it impossible to verify the process of rate-setting, or to investigate the possibility of unequal pay for equal work. Following this discovery, the riders began to capture instances of low wages which seemed to show algorithmic bias on the basis of various factors. This was followed on by an effort by the IWGB to monitor where pay fell short of minimum wages.¹⁰⁰ It informed their collective efforts to organise to shift rates upwards.

B. Algorithmic Racial Discrimination

1. AI-Related Problem in the Workplace

A second risk is algorithmic racial profiling, which occurs when AI-driven or automated systems contribute to unjustified different treatment or impacts disavouring people based on their race or ethnicity. This can result from facial recognition systems, or from less direct measures such as taking workers' postcodes into account to inform decisions.¹⁰¹ It has been alleged that AI profiling systems have resulted in the automatic dismissal or “robofiring” of people from platforms, due to systems' inability

⁹⁹ Gallagher, C., Gregory, K. & Karabaliyev, B. (2023) *Digital worker inquiry and the critical potential of participatory worker data science for on-demand platform workers*. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 1–21

¹⁰⁰ *Revealed: The Scottish Deliveroo riders earning less than minimum wage*. <https://theferret.scot/deliveroo-riders-earning-less-than-minimum-wage/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁰¹ Buolamwini et al, (2020), *Facial recognition technologies: A primer*. https://global-uploads.webflow.com/5e027ca188c99e3515b404b7/5ed1002058516c11edc66a14_FRTsPrimerMay2020.pdf, accessed 22.05.2024.

to fairly read a range of skin tones.¹⁰² Research has established that facial-analysis software has much higher error rates when analysing people with darker-skin compared to those with lighter-skin, and women compared with men.¹⁰³ There is a risk that such systems, operating at different stages in the work relationship – hiring, wage setting, evaluation, discipline, or dismissal – either discriminate through mimicking racial stereotypes, or discriminate through the AI’s uneven treatment of people.¹⁰⁴ The particular issue of facial recognition technologies is an example of the wider set of race-based and other discriminatory risks associated with certain AI technologies.

2.1 Perspective of Workers, Worker Advocacy Groups, and Trade Unions on the Issue

An audit of four facial recognition systems in India found high error rates, and one of the unions has brought a case against Uber.¹⁰⁵ In the UK, the worker advocacy group Worker Info Exchange claims that UberEats has dismissed people automatically using biometric software developed by Microsoft.¹⁰⁶ The Independent Workers of Great Britain union has similarly said that racial profiling had mistakenly led to at least 36 drivers having their registration with Uber terminated since the start of the pandemic,

¹⁰² Uber facing new UK driver claims of racial discrimination.

<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2021/oct/06/uber-facing-new-uk-driver-claims-of-racial-discrimination>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁰³ Study finds gender and skin-type bias in commercial artificial-intelligence systems.

<https://news.mit.edu/2018/study-finds-gender-skin-type-bias-artificial-intelligence-systems-0212>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁰⁴ “AI can operate at several stages in the work relationship, including hiring, wage setting, evaluation, promotion, discipline, and dismissal. If algorithms are constructed that embody insidious racial or gender stereotypes, then women or people of color will be seriously disadvantaged in the labor market.”

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3410655, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁰⁵ Uber driver claims job loss from faulty face detection, Uber claims compliance violation,

<https://www.indiatimes.com/technology/news/india-driver-loses-job-uber-facial-recognition-fails-537477.html#:~:text=Uber's%20facial%20comparison%20tool%20helps.as%20long%20or%20cropped%20hair:Uber's%20facial%20recognition%20is%20locking%20Indian%20drivers%20out%20of%20their%20accounts/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁰⁶ We're challenging Uber's racially discriminatory facial recognition system,

<https://www.workerinfoexchange.org/post/we-re-challenging-uber-s-racially-discriminatory-facial-recognition-system>; UK: Uber drivers file claim for compensation over “racist” facial recognition technology. <https://www.business-humanrights.org/en/latest-news/uk-uber-drivers-file-claims-for-compensation-over-racist-facial-recognition-technology/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

and is calling for Uber to scrap the “racist algorithm” and to reinstate terminated drivers.¹⁰⁷ Where individual workers have appealed against decisions, the lack of regulation means that the risk of error is borne by the worker. One study of facial recognition of Uber drivers in the US concluded that, “accountability for identity verification is shifted to the workers, who bear the consequences for systemic failures”.¹⁰⁸ This instance of demutualised risk highlights that even where workers do not experience direct harms, they bear the insecurity and risk associated with systems that are known to err.¹⁰⁹

2.2 Perspective of the Platform Related to Racial Discrimination

Defenders of facial recognition technology, and developers such as the Onfido system used by Deliveroo, have insisted that they are able to iron out demographic bias.¹¹⁰ Microsoft has said that corporations using its facial recognition software – such as Uber – should incorporate “meaningful human review to detect and resolve cases of misidentification or other failure”.¹¹¹ Later, Microsoft discontinued the software it had developed, because it was inaccurate.¹¹² Uber continues to use the software, and has said there are two manual human reviews prior to any decision to remove a driver and

¹⁰⁷ *Uber facing new UK driver claims of racial discrimination.*

<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2021/oct/06/uber-facing-new-uk-driver-claims-of-racial-discrimination>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁰⁸ *Uber’s facial recognition is locking Indian drivers out of their accounts.*

<https://www.technologyreview.com/2022/12/06/1064287/ubers-facial-recognition-is-locking-indian-drivers-out-of-their-accounts/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁰⁹ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁰ *The flawed claims about bias in facial recognition,* <https://www.lawfareblog.com/flawed-claims-about-bias-facial-recognition>; *Deliveroo to onboard drivers with Onfido’s biometric technology.* <https://findbiometrics.com/deliveroo-to-onboard-drivers-with-onfidos-biometric-tech-910061>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹¹¹ *UK: Uber drivers file claims for compensation over “racist” facial recognition technology.* <https://www.business-humanrights.org/en/latest-news/uk-uber-drivers-file-claims-for-compensation-over-racist-facial-recognition-technology/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹¹² *Microsoft is scrapping some bad A.I. facial recognition tools.*

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/korihale/2022/07/05/microsoft-is-scrapping-some-bad-ai-facial-recognition-tools/?sh=769090ca6b54>, accessed 22.05.2024.

the system is “fair and important for the safety of our platform”. It has also said anyone removed from the platform could appeal against the decision.¹¹³

3. General Principles That Could Inform Regulation in This Area

Racial profiling is clearly a case where anti-discrimination regulation could be used to avert and mitigate risks. Yet in the US, legal experts said in 2020 that racial profiling in a work context is largely unaddressed by existing antidiscrimination law: “If it is an algorithm that is producing the discriminatory outcome, rather than a human decision maker, it may be nearly impossible for the worker who is adversely affected to mount a successful legal challenge.”¹¹⁴

4. How These Principles Are Currently Embedded in UK Regulation and Law

In the UK and Europe, court cases are beginning to challenge the use of facial recognition and biometric systems. Worker advocacy group Worker Info Exchange are pursuing the case of P. E. Manjang, an UberEats driver who, they allege, was victimised under the Equality Act 2010.¹¹⁵ The judge in the case said: “The case essentially concerns facial recognition, [and] its consequences on an individual’s access to work and whether the processes engaged by the Respondent [Uber] create racial disadvantage.”¹¹⁶ Ascertaining these facts depended on answering questions about the algorithmic processes that impacted the worker.¹¹⁷ He noted the “lack of clarity” about

¹¹³ <https://www.uber.com/en-GB/blog/real-time-id-check-uk-drivers/>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹¹⁴ *The invisible web at work: Artificial intelligence and electronic surveillance in the workplace.* https://scholarship.law.unc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1003&context=aidr_collection, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹¹⁵ *First case: WIX Uber case of P. E. Manjang: claims are for harassment related to race under s.26 Equality Act 2010, victimisation under s.27 Equality Act 2010 and indirect race discrimination under s.19 Equality Act 2021.* <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/uber-eats-sued-over-racist-facial-recognition-checks-5ck72nq2w>, accessed 22.05.2024.

<https://www.workerinfoexchange.org/post/we-re-challenging-uber-s-racially-discriminatory-facial-recognition-system>

¹¹⁶ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/62dab66b8fa8f5649dbef494/Mr_P_E_Manjang_-_v_Uber_Eats_UK_Ltd_Others_-_3206212_2021_-_Preliminary_Judgment.pdf p.20

¹¹⁷ *Ibid.*, the judge said: “At the point of presentation there was a lack of clarity about what the processes were that had led to the deactivation.”

processes that led to the deactivation.¹¹⁸ The case is unresolved, but provides an example of an initiative based on evidence gathered through GDPR being deployed within current employment regulatory frameworks to challenge algorithmic discrimination.

5. How AI Risk Frameworks and AI Regulation Might Be Relevant to These Questions

Since it seems impossible to ensure that any biometric algorithmic system would not discriminate on grounds of race, avoiding the risk of racial profiling seems to require the prohibition of the use of biometric data to authenticate the identities of platform workers.¹¹⁹ Short of this, across AI regulation, one of the principles that seems to be necessary is for workers to become aware of how the systems they work under operate. Another principle would be to ensure that no automatic dismissal or other detriment should occur using biometric data. Some groups go further and say that given the inscrutability of algorithmic systems that use biometric data, data should only be collected with it is necessary and essential for workers to do their jobs.¹²⁰ It is also worth considering what kind of human review, and processes for appeal, if any, could prevent the risks of algorithmic discrimination. The need to go through a process of appealing could itself constitute a form of discrimination, particularly if it was unpaid, and place a disproportionate burden on people with certain racial characteristics. This is clearly, therefore, an area that demands a set of guiding

¹¹⁸ *Uber Eats treats drivers as ‘numbers not humans’, says dismissed UK courier.*

<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2022/jul/27/uber-eats-treats-drivers-as-numbers-not-humans-says-dismissed-courier>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹¹⁹ *In its submission on the European Platform Work Directive, Worker Info Exchange recommended that “the use of biometric data to authenticate the identity of platform workers should be prohibited. The collection and processing of biometric data (whether using 1–1 verification or 1–n identification) to authenticate the identity of platform workers is unnecessary and disproportionate. The inaccuracy of facial recognition technologies such as the Microsoft Azure Face API used by Uber has been widely demonstrated, especially when used on people of colour and other minoritised groups. However, even when these systems work as intended, they pose a huge and unnecessary risk, by collecting, processing, and often storing the sensitive biometric data of workers. Other methods for authenticating identity exist which are less intrusive, equally or even more reliable, and which do not present the same set of risks as biometric authentication.* <https://www.workerinfoexchange.org/workers-recommendations-on-eu-directive>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹²⁰ *Annette Bernhardt, Lisa Kresge, Reem Suleiman, “Data and Algorithms at Work”, Berkeley Labor Centre, 2021.* <https://laborcenter.berkeley.edu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Data-and-Algorithms-at-Work.pdf>, p.21

principles for regulation that apply across the spheres of employment, data rights, and AI regulation.

The UK Government has also explored the issue of data-driven discrimination and bias in decision-making in some detail. In November 2020, the government completed a review of bias in algorithmic decision-making.¹²¹ It suggested that one of the answers to biased technologies was having a more “diverse” workforce able “to interrogate biases that may arise throughout the process of developing, deploying and operating an algorithmic decision-making tool”.¹²² It noted that EHRC does not have a particular programme of work looking at “the implications of new technologies for... decision making in the workplace”, and recommended that “the EHRC should ensure that it has the capacity and capability to investigate algorithmic discrimination against protected groups”.¹²³ The government sees no place for unions or workers’ collectives in such oversight.

6. How Workers, Within or in the Absence of Regulation, Are Taking Autonomous Action to Address the Risk

The organisation Worker Info Exchange has carried out various initiatives to gather cases of racial profiling and take these cases to court to challenge algorithmic racial discrimination. In the prominent case mentioned above, P. E. Manjang took Uber to an employment tribunal claiming racial harassment under the Equality Act 2010 and indirect race discrimination under the Equality Act 2021. The reason for his termination was that Uber’s facial recognition system failed to recognise him when he tried to sign in for work and took disciplinary measures against him on the supposition that he had given his account to someone else to use.¹²⁴ After his termination, Manjang

¹²¹ *Review into bias in algorithmic decision-making.*

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/957259/Review_into_bias_in_algorithmic_decision-making.pdf, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹²² *Ibid.*, p.87

¹²³ *Ibid.*, p.27

¹²⁴ *We’re challenging Uber’s racially discriminatory facial recognition system.*

<https://www.workerinfoexchange.org/post/we-re-challenging-uber-s-racially-discriminatory-facial-recognition-system>, accessed 22.05.2024.

was able to obtain selfies of himself through GDPR subject access requests, all of which were of him. Worker Info Exchange, in presenting the case, highlighted a range of evidence about the racial bias of the system. This evidence was insufficient to establish details of the process which led to his automatic dismissal.¹²⁵

IV. A Review of UK and EU Approaches to Regulating AI in Relation to Platform Work

The UK Government's approach to the regulation of AI is currently captured in a 10-year plan to "make Britain a global AI superpower" and, as such, is contextualised in the language of innovation, growing businesses, and harnessing the power of technology to solve problems.¹²⁶ The government has established a set of regulatory principles for digital regulation,¹²⁷ but at present they do not speak to the issues and risks facing workers. Instead, these principles are grounded in driving growth and competition, ensuring that innovation does not harm businesses or citizens, and protecting fundamental rights and freedoms.

In the short- and long-term, the UK Government plans to set standards to govern AI through a National AI Strategy.¹²⁸ The government is also planning to complete an in-depth analysis on algorithmic transparency, with a view to developing a cross-government Standard for Algorithmic Transparency. The Standard, developed by the [Central Digital and Data Office](#) and the [Centre for Data Ethics and Innovation](#), is meant to "[help] public sector organisations provide clear information about algorithmic tools they use to support decisions". Having presented examples of the

¹²⁵ *Uber Eats treats drivers as 'numbers not humans', says dismissed UK courier.*

<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2022/jul/27/uber-eats-treats-drivers-as-numbers-not-humans-says-dismissed-courier>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹²⁶ *National AI strategy.* <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-ai-strategy/national-ai-strategy-html-version>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹²⁷ *Plan for digital regulation: Developing an outcomes monitoring framework.* <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/digital-regulation-driving-growth-and-unlocking-innovation/plan-for-digital-regulation-developing-an-outcomes-monitoring-framework>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹²⁸ *National AI Strategy* <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-ai-strategy/national-ai-strategy-html-version>, accessed 22.05.2024.

tool's use, the government plans to pilot an AI Standards Hub to coordinate UK engagement in AI standardisation globally.¹²⁹

While workers' rights are not central to current UK Government plans to regulate AI, the Government's skills agenda is connecting its AI agenda with its workforce policy. It has short- and medium-term plans to support data science and digital skills through Education Skills Bootcamps (short-term), and to publish research that explores what skills are needed to enable employees to use AI in business settings and identifies how national skills provision can meet those needs (medium-term).¹³⁰ The UK Government also proposes to support a broader range of workers to enter AI-related jobs by ensuring that career pathways highlight opportunities to work with or develop AI. Within each proposal, the possible ramifications of AI development for workers and for the labour market as a whole could be acknowledged and explored, and the capacity of workers to address and avoid work-related risks could be supported.¹³¹ "Fair work principles" could be incorporated into policy.^{132,133} These principles strive to future proof jobs, stressing the importance of building fair production networks, striving for equity, enhancing safety, ensuring the explainability of AI systems, and supporting workers to build their collective voice.

The Trades Union Congress (TUC) offers some guidance on how work and AI regulation can be conceptualised and regulated.¹³⁴ These reports stress the urgency of consulting workers in the process of developing regulatory frameworks, as well as

¹²⁹ Gov.UK data labs. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/govuk-data-labs-cabinet-office-related-links/govuk-data-labs-cabinet-office-related-links>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹³⁰ UK Government National AI Strategy, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/614db4d1e90e077a2cbdf3c4/National_AI_Strategy_-_PDF_version.pdf, pp. 8-9

¹³¹ Gov.UK data labs. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/govuk-data-labs-cabinet-office-related-links/govuk-data-labs-cabinet-office-related-links>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹³² AI for fair work report. <https://fair.work/wp-content/uploads/sites/17/2022/12/AI-for-fair-work-report-edited.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹³³ Scottish fair work framework. <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2022/12/fair-work-action-plan-becoming-leading-fair-work-nation-2025/documents/fair-work-action-plan-becoming-leading-fair-work-nation-2025/fair-work-action-plan-becoming-leading-fair-work-nation-2025/govscot%3Adocument/fair-work-action-plan-becoming-leading-fair-work-nation-2025.pdf>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹³⁴ TUC reports dignity at work and the AI revolution. <https://www.tuc.org.uk/research-analysis/reports/dignity-work-and-ai-revolution>, accessed 22.05.2024.

consulting the increasing evidence base being developed through worker experiences with AI technologies.¹³⁵ They also stress the importance of understanding the long-term effects of AI on work, workers, wellbeing, and employment rights.

Understandably, this guidance emphasises the capacity of AI to pose significant risks to workers, including inequality and discrimination, unsafe working conditions, and unhealthy blurring of the boundaries between home and work.

Beyond the UK, the EU has put forward the EU AI Act (AIA), which would create horizontal regulation for AI systems in the EU, classifying AI use by risk level.¹³⁶ The ETUI has generated a helpful visualisation of these risk levels:¹³⁷

Figure 2. ETUI's Elaboration of The AI Regulation Risk-Based Approach¹³⁸

¹³⁵ Technology managing people – The worker experience

<https://www.tuc.org.uk/research-analysis/reports/technology-managing-people-worker-experience>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹³⁶ "The EU AI Act (AIA) proposes a horizontal regulation for AI systems in the EU. The initial draft of the AIA was released in April 2021. The EU Council provided its updated consensus draft in December 2022. The AIA classifies AI use by risk level (unacceptable, high, limited, and minimal) and describes documentation, auditing, and process requirements for each risk level. The AIA is currently in committee and subject to discussion around increasing consumer protections, defining AI, carving out appropriate exceptions, and more"

<https://www.responsible.ai/post/eu-ai-act-explained>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹³⁷ The AI Regulation: Entering an AI regulatory winter? <https://www.etui.org/publications/ai-regulation-entering-ai-regulatory-winter>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹³⁸ Figure taken from: The AI Regulation: Entering an AI regulatory winter?

The European Union's *Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence*¹³⁹ includes among its list of high-risk AI systems those deployed in “employment, worker management, and access to self-employment”, where they are intended to be used for “making decisions on promotion and termination of work-related contractual relationships, for task allocation and for monitoring and evaluating performance and behaviour of persons in such relationships”.¹⁴⁰ According to these rules, AI-driven systems used in food distribution fall under the high-risk category, however they function, whenever they “pose a high risk of harm to the health and safety or the fundamental rights of persons, taking into account both the severity of the possible harm and its probability of occurrence”. This rule raises further questions as to whether any “fundamental rights” are being violated in cases of algorithmic wage discrimination or racial profiling, where actions of the platform result in their dismissal.¹⁴¹

While these provisions do not apply in the United Kingdom, the principle of risk-based regulation tends to stipulate that where there is a high risk of certain principles being violated, then systems need to be monitored and measured, and any risks mitigated.¹⁴² But such monitoring and measuring in turn raises a series of further issues and problems: Who would be doing the measuring? What would be measured? What kind of regulatory framework would help mitigate the risk of mistakes in what is measured and monitored? Who monitors the monitors? A full survey of the means of monitoring AI systems and their relationship to wages and other forms of discrimination is beyond this report's scope, but one straightforward option involves enabling workers to monitor algorithms, measure rates they are paid, and mitigate the risk of unfair payment by being able to compare pay with that of others. This is how wage monitoring and detection of wage discrimination happens in many workplaces.¹⁴³ It is a

<https://www.etui.org/publications/ai-regulation-entering-ai-regulatory-winter>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹³⁹ <https://lexpency.org/eu/52021PC0206/PRE/#5-31>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁴⁰ https://lexpency.org/eu/52021PC0206/ANX_III/, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁴¹ <https://lexpency.org/eu/52021PC0206/PRE/#5-31>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁴² <https://www.responsible.ai/post/eu-ai-act-explained>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁴³ International Labour Organisation, (2022), *Pay transparency legislation: Implications for employers' and workers' organizations*, 2022. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_protect/---protrav/---travail/documents/publication/wcms_849209.pdf, accessed 22.05.2024.

principle that was invoked by Worker Info Exchange in relation to a case for Uber workers, who are classified as workers, to access data to verify their payment of the minimum wage.¹⁴⁴

Where gig workers do not have employment rights, then data access and AI-system monitoring requires a different regulatory or legislative basis, perhaps drawn from the provisions of the GDPR, or through introducing new kinds of AI regulation linked with working arrangements. As in other parts of the economy, platform workers need genuine, verifiable understanding of pay rates to establish whether there is wage discrimination in a given situation. This is a core principle which regulation – whether employment regulation, data rights, or AI regulation – should ultimately support. And, where wage discrimination is identified through monitoring, then regulators should provide workers with routes to rectifying it, supported by regulators where necessary.

V. Principles and Recommendations to Ensure Workers' Influence in Regulatory Debates

The notion of “risk” underpins most recent regulatory efforts in the sphere of AI. It is useful in the context of shaping regulation of AI in platform work. Draft regulation developed by the European Parliament classifies some AI-driven practices in the employment context as high risk. Regulatory frameworks and proposals do not adequately address risks and harms that have been discussed. This reflects the high level at which current regulatory frameworks have been developed, most notably at EU level.

Addressing real risks requires new evidence and policy that takes account of workers' experiences of these systems.

¹⁴⁴ “The applicants state that they have the following interests in their requests: the British court has ruled that drivers are entitled to a minimum wage and holiday allowance. In order to calculate their wages, applicants need access to their data.” [Dutch court rules on data transparency for Uber and Ola drivers - Ekker Advocatuur: Uber-drivers-v.-Uber-transparency-requests-.docx \(live.com\)](#), accessed 22.05.2024.

In addressing risks, however, there is a tendency to focus on compliance with standards – obtained or ascertained through audits, checklists, and other cursory measuring processes – rather than enshrining rules and principles that reflect rights which workers have consistently fought for and won. Where governance does require a process of monitoring, legal scholars have suggested that governance should be participatory, involving “bottom-up approaches that promote multi-stakeholder involvement in order to ensure that due process and fundamental rights are respected in the work context”.¹⁴⁵

This report does not undertake a detailed assessment of the full suite of potential risks emerging from AI-related developments in platform work, or of future AI regulations that might be applied to platform work. Instead, its discussion points towards principles, based on practical cases, that can and should guide regulation of AI-driven systems that impact platform workers.

While identification of categories of risk can fit within a framework of risks, particular instances of the impact of AI-driven technologies on platform workers can only be established by workers themselves. Without workers challenging certain cases, then, regulatory frameworks do not clearly result in the practical enforcement of rules. There are therefore a number of prerequisites to effective and meaningful regulation of this area.

One prerequisite is that workers must have the tools, techniques, and training to see and understand instances where regulation is an effective means for redressing grievances. This requires infrastructure, as well as regulations, to enable workers to gather information. Often identifying these problems and grievances requires comparison between workers”, since, by definition, discrimination involves comparing the situations of different parties.

A second prerequisite is that workers have the rights and routes to engage collectively with one another to gather information, to ascertain risks and discrimination, and to

¹⁴⁵ *Between risk mitigation and labour rights enforcement: Assessing the transatlantic race to govern AI-driven decision-making through a comparative lens.* https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4337517, accessed 22.05.2024.

engage with regulators. Such information-gathering, risk-analysis, and engagement requires that workers have the means and technologies to obtain information. This will involve research and other inquiries that enable workers to monitor and measure their algorithmic management.

The third prerequisite of effective regulation, then, is for such research and inquiries to be developed. Such independent initiatives can be replicated, opening possibilities of integrated or inter-connected series of inquiries that enable the monitoring of risks of AI on a wider scale.

Given these prerequisites, three further principles can underpin meaningful regulation:

1. Grievance Principle

Every worker should be able to raise concerns and have those concerns answered. Where those concerns relate to AI-related risks, this should be verified. Where that verification seems dubious, an ombudsman – or a steward, akin to a health and safety rep – should investigate.

2. Knowledge Principle

Every platform worker should have the right to information equivalent to that enshrined in clause 1 of the Employment Act, i.e. particulars of employment. This should be granted in addition to the information required to be given through GDPR.

3. Bargaining Principle

Platform workers should have data they need to bargain about ADM and AI, as workers have the right in other parts of the economy to bargain about new technologies and forms of control and management. The capacity to pool data is essential to the capacity to bargain and should not be obstructed. This can be described as co-producing evidence.

These prerequisites and principles would go some way to providing the grounds for a regulatory system that is practically useful, and links with the experiences of workers on the ground.

This report has demonstrated that there is a significant regulatory gap concerning issues facing platform workers in on-demand food distribution. What regulation there is tends not to synchronise with other regulatory dimensions, and even where there is regulation, it often does not touch on local experiences, or provide workers with the capacity to ascertain the risks they face. In light of this, we have three key recommendations for developing regulation.

Key recommendations: The development of regulation that addresses concrete risks faced by platform workers in the on-demand food distribution sector should be:

- Data driven
- Locally led
- Participative

These recommendations relate to three gaps. There is a data gap because data about the risks such as algorithmic wage discrimination or racial profiling is not accessible or gathered. There is a local gap because the current regulatory spheres do not touch on local situations, whereas the efforts of workers from below to address risks are often led by workers in response to their local situations. There is a participation gap because regulation tends not to enable or empower workers to address risks and to use regulations to address issues arising from their work.

The cases that we have illustrated in Dunfermline, and with Worker Info Exchange, highlight that autonomous initiatives of workers demonstrate the regulatory gap. In these cases, for regulation to have a meaningful effect, regulators have to interact with the workers who are challenging their conditions, through data-driven, local, participative processes.

● ● ● Further Questions

This report has explored existing and known risks in on-demand delivery work from the perspective of workers and their representatives, but we have not explored the role that industry might play in mitigating work-related risks, particularly at the local level, or how worker-led projects could play a more influential role within industry. There is, generally, an antagonism between platform companies and workers that stems not only from the issue of employment misclassification, but also from the persistent refusal of platform companies to acknowledge worker concerns, particularly about safety, financial risks, and discrimination. This is in addition to the antagonism that is latent in most industrial settings, characterised by an unequal power relationship between employers and workers. These dynamics raise key concerns about the ability of platform companies to meaningfully respond to workers' concerns regarding AI and its regulation moving forward, and also prompt the question of how industry can genuinely collaborate with workers to tackle grievances.

Currently, the onus is on individuals to prove or to generate evidence of control and work-related risks. This arrangement has given rise to a number of worker-led projects and initiatives, but these projects do not inform industry or regulatory responses. Despite their immediate value for workers and the rich potential for the evidence generated by worker-led tools to inform our understanding of how AI and automated systems do and do not function, there is currently no substantive incentive or imperative for industry to meaningfully respond.

Platform companies benefit from an asymmetrical power dynamic over workers, and proprietary data and automated systems sit at the heart of that dynamic. The current UK government regulations on AI do not help to balance this dynamic, but rather “empower existing regulators – such as the Health and Safety Executive, Equality and Human Rights Commission and Competition and Markets Authority – to come up with tailored, context-specific approaches that suit the way AI is actually being used in their

sectors”.¹⁴⁶ It is unclear how this approach will ensure that self-employed individuals who work for on-demand platforms will be protected by these existing regulators. There are clear questions about the capacity of regulators to enforce industry-specific regulation and to ensure or monitor compliance. While a number of robust recommendations and principles for fair and good work in platforms exist, it remains unclear how these principles would be enforced and maintained.¹⁴⁷ In the meantime, workers will continue to develop autonomous initiatives to address the risks of AI-driven work.

¹⁴⁶ UK unveils world leading approach to innovation in first artificial intelligence white paper to turbocharge growth. <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/uk-unveils-world-leading-approach-to-innovation-in-first-artificial-intelligence-white-paper-to-turbocharge-growth>, accessed 22.05.2024.

¹⁴⁷ See the Institute for the Future of Work Lab for a comprehensive list of principles and resources to support workers and companies. <https://www.ifow.org/landing-page/the-lab>, accessed 22.05.2024.

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